

Black Sea- Data Management Plan.

Data Management Plan Checklist

Dataset Overview	
Dataset Title	EMSO EUXINUS
Dataset Description	Black Sea Node is a important contribution by Romania to growing marine network of real time-data system deployed in the Black Sea. The purpose of this data set is to provide meteorological and oceanographic data hourly form 3 offshore moored system. These data are used for scientific studies and environmental monitoring of the western Black Sea.
Process Flow Title	Moored buoy
Data Catalog link	http://www.euxinus.eu/login_page.html
Date of First Version	07.10.2021

Data Collection
What data will you collect or create?
Meteorological parameters, current parameters, conductivity, temperature, pressure, oxygen, turbidity and chlorophyl, are stored in local data base, and can be shared using web-based service and also data retrieving services. The format of the data that can be shared as excel file and ASCII standard formats.
How will the data be collected or created?
The satellite communication segment is the link between the buoy and the coordination centre. The transmission mode is adopted for standard communication: the buoy sent the message to a satellite modem to the coordination centre. Data received are decompressed and stored in database. The quality control is done in real time, automatic and offline by specialized personal.

Documentation and Metadata
What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?
It is planned to fully align with the ERDDAP applications and follow guidelines from Data Management team. The dataset entries can be found in the EMSO_EUXINUS database, excel sheet.

Ethics and Legal Compliance
How will you manage any ethical issues?
The instruments and data collected by these instruments is owned by the GeoEcoMar. In the EMSO-EUXINUS data base, are stored only data coming from this infrastructure.
How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?
Two ownership categories have been identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <u>Open Data</u>: The standard suite of instruments and any data generated by these instruments are owned by the GeoEcoMar. These data are classified as Open data.• <u>Academic Research Data</u>: Data may be stored and disseminated by GeoEcoMar for Academic Research, but remains under the ownership of the research institute.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

The data are stored and backed up following standard GeoEcoMar and future data strategy recommendations on these requirements.

The storage equipment is operated and maintained by the EMSO EUXINUS Black Sea team.

How will you manage access and security?

The main suite of instruments produce data that is classified as open data. These data are freely available to the public via the GeoEcoMar website (historic files) or online data feeds (Real time streams). The data access is based on request and is facilitated using an VPN connection. This requires secure access procedures is in place.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

All the data collected will be kept long term.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

The data will be retained indefinitely.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

Data is available online, via the EMODNET Physics website: [EMODNET](#) and [EUXINUS](#). Also, an similar to push service, is available for real time data sharing.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Based on officially request, there are no restrictions on sharing this data.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Raluca Radulescu - Data Management responsible

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

- IT support